

1 **Sting1 is silenced completely in embryonic stem cells.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
8 STING silencing which occurred concomitant with lineage specification in embryonic stem cells of the
9 human embryo. We measured changes in other innate immune receptors, including NLR and TLR family
10 genes, and non-N/TLR receptors like AIM2, cGAS, MAVS, Rig-I (DDX58), MDA5 (IFIH1), and LGP2
11 (DHX58). The MHC class I transcriptional activator NLRC5 was modestly active. Tlr5, a flagellin receptor,
12 was active, as was Tlr2.

13 Citations

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15 Sato, T., Ohteki, T., Hayakawa, Y., Barber, G.N. and Kurokawa, M., 2015. Bacterial c-di-GMP affects
16 hematopoietic stem/progenitors and their niches through STING. Cell reports, 11(1), pp.71-84.
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